

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION CULTURE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article describes various methods of improving communication culture among students. Also, the possibilities of improving the communication culture of students, the ways of educating the model of behavior corresponding to the actions expected from each of the people affected by mutual communication are described in detail.

Key words: communication, culture of communication, communication, logic, tact, social activity, imitation at a young age.

We understand today that communication culture in a person is defined as a process. The transmission of information occurs because the source of the information acts on it. Relating to established concepts and theories of psychology and bringing them into communication is logic. The psychology of communication is a human thing related to intelligence and harmony. It is possible to learn and use this understanding in developing successful communication maps. When I take communication skills classes, I feel that it is more about the purpose and formation of my messages than the language I use to communicate. The students do not appreciate me or my communication. Obviously, recognition is achieved through the words that reach them, but the real connection to effective communication is the psychology behind it. This made me realize that there is a great opportunity to work on the culture of communication. Communication refers to the effort to connect with another, and psychology is a behavioral science. Gone are the times when human behavior was unknown - we observed it internally and concepts were established. In the same way, the psychology of communication is clearly visible. I am not someone who gives a

model of the psychology of communication. It is an attempt to broaden the understanding of psychology's role in communication.

Psychology and communication go hand in hand and fill the gap in understanding complex behavior in all areas of life. We need to anticipate behavior. Understanding the psychology of communication is like making a single color out of the multiples scattered around us. It is a combination of felt-observed-written and reflected things. Communication is an important condition of human life and activity. It is with the help of communication that people have the opportunity to work together to reduce their nature and satisfy their individual needs. In the process of communication, certain images and models of human behavior are formed, and later they become part of a person. A person's thinking, the ability to analyze and evaluate the world and his image is formed in the process of communication. The Polish psychologist E. Melibruda, who made a detailed assessment of this problem, states the following: "Communication is as important as air for us in interpersonal relations."

Research methodology. In the article, it is very difficult to give a single correct definition to the communication culture of students as it is a very complex process. Therefore, the content of the concept of communication can usually be defined by emphasizing some of its aspects:

A) communication - the process of establishing and developing communication, characterized by the need for cooperative activity.

B) communication - interaction of subjects through the sign system.

Analysis and results: In the textbook "General Psychology" published under the editorship of psychologist A.V. Petrovsky, communication is recognized as a process consisting of information exchange, interaction and mutual understanding between two or more people.

In the textbook "General Psychology" published by M.G.Davletshin, it is stated that communication is an interaction between two or more people

consisting of the exchange of information of an affective evaluative nature and knowledge. Published under the direction of M.G.Davletshin. In the short explanatory dictionary of Psychology, communication is defined as follows: communication is the interaction of two or more people.

In accordance with the above definitions, communication can be generally defined as follows: communication is a process of interaction between at least two people, during which information is exchanged, relations are established and developed.

The importance of communication in human life is immeasurable. A human child becomes a person in the process of communicating and interacting with others. Through communication, a person acquires social experience and culture. If a newborn person is deprived of the opportunity to communicate with others, he will never become a person, that is, he will lag behind in his mental development. After all, human mental development begins with communication. Human society cannot exist without communication. It is communication that forms a community of individuals working together. It is necessary to communicate between individuals in order to create a plan of cooperation and realize it. Collaborative activities are organized and implemented through communication. At the same time, new relations and connections are formed between people during the activity. So, communication and activity are closely related. When people engage in communication, they ask questions, give orders, request, explain something, and at the same time set the goal of influencing others and explaining this to them. The goal of communication reflects the need for people to work together. In this case, communication is manifested as interpersonal interaction, that is, a set of communication and interactions that arise in the process of joint activity of people. Joint activity and communication takes place under conditions of social control. Society has developed a structure of special behavior patterns as social norms. One person can play different roles in different communication tasks. For

example, there is a director in the workplace, a patient who obeys the doctor's instructions when he is sick, a good child of elderly parents in a family, a hospitable family head. The interaction of people in different roles is governed by role expectations. Whether he likes it or not, the people around him expect him to behave in accordance with a certain pattern. The condition for the immediate success of the culture of communication is to maintain a model of behavior that corresponds to the actions expected from each of the interacting people. The ability of a person to copy what others expect from him, what he is ready to hear and see in him is called tact. It is known that tact is an important component in pedagogical activity. In particular, the pedagogical process is based on the organized activities of teachers and students. Therefore, the teacher should not forget that the pedagogical process is made up of a group of students and should not neglect the personality of each student. The loss of psychological contact with students, even for a short period of time, causes serious consequences.

The development of communication culture in higher education institutions is a complex socio-psychological process, which does not consist only of imitating the speech heard by a person, but is also related to the development of communication culture in students and the need for communication. and the content of this activity and the extent to which it is organized have an effective effect on development. Because during properly organized cultural communication activities and daily interactions with the surrounding people, the mental, physical and moral development of the child improves. That is why knowing children's social activity and forming useful habits in the child , the organization of communication culture mechanisms is a decisive factor in the development of positive character traits.

In conclusion, it should be said that the culture of communication can be formed from a young age in the family, under the influence of the social environment, as a result of awareness and upbringing. The fact that we adults are

role models for young people comes from our communication with each other. From golden words (my dear, turn around, learn, you are very wonderful, today you are different, you have opened up, your clothes fit very well) in our daily life. we need to use more.

By imitating the communication of adults, young people develop the art of communication and culture in them. When forming the culture of personal communication, it is necessary to take into account the person's age, gender, profession, and worldview. So, communication is formed in an integral connection with thinking

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